

EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INDUCTION PROGRAM FOR BEGINNING TEACHERS (IPBT) IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF MARINDUQUE

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the Extent of Implementation of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) in the Division of Marinduque, focusing on its four areas: Common and Specific Topics, Mentoring, Differentiated Supervision, and Formal Classroom Observation. It also investigates significant differences in IPBT implementation across eight districts within the Division. Further, this determines problems encountered by the respondents during the program implementation and their solutions to address the problems. This involved 113 teachers who completed the IPBT from eight Districts in the Division. Electronic and hard copies of the researcher's questionnaire were administered, retrieved, and the data were run through statistical analyses such as the weighted mean, F-test, and Chi-square test. Findings indicate a Great Extent of IPBT implementation overall in the Division, with each area showing a Great Extent of implementation. Meanwhile, statistically significant differences exist in the implementation of IPBT across districts at a .05 level of significance. Common problems encountered by the respondents include workload conflicts in common and specific topics, scheduling issues in mentoring, confusion over differentiated instruction techniques, and inadequate feedback in classroom observations. The respondent's solutions to address these challenges include providing sufficient time for module completion, scheduling mentor-mentee meetings, offering technical support for differentiated instruction, and improving communication regarding classroom observation schedules. Moreover, the study proposes an enhancement program aligned with DepEd Order No. 43, series of 2017, aiming to improve the IPBT implementation process in the Division of Marinduque.

Keywords: *Differentiated Supervision, Extent, Formal Classroom Observation, Implementation, Intervention and Mentoring.*

INTRODUCTION

Induction programs are implemented by schools worldwide to guide and support newly hired or beginning teachers in their first years of teaching and to contribute to their well-being and professional development (Partlow, 2006). The beginning years of newly hired teachers seem crucial and highly challenging. The first year of teaching is the time for them to apply and develop their learned knowledge and acquired skills in tertiary education in a real-life setting.

One of the studies conducted by Bilbao et al. (2013) regarding the implementation of an Induction Program reveals that a Teacher Induction Program has a positive effect on newly hired teachers in enhancing their knowledge, skills, values, and commitment to the profession and in turn also improve student's learning outcomes. To continuously support the continuing professional development and progress of newly hired teachers, the Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 43 series of 2017 on August 11, 2017, which provides guidelines on implementing the Teacher's Induction Program (TIP). The Teacher Induction Program (TIP) for newly hired teachers, through the Teacher Education Council (TEC), issues the Teacher Induction Program Policy on the implementation of the TIP with the commitment of developing newly hired teachers (with three years and below in the service). It aims to support and assist freshly hired teachers in having positive impacts on the three (3) sets of outcomes, namely: (1) teacher commitment and retention, (2) teacher's classroom instructional practices, and (3) student Achievement.

In addition, under Republic Act 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 Section 7, states that "the Department of Education together with the Commission of Higher Education (CHED) and in partnership with other government entities in the academe industry and non-government organizations (NGOs) shall conduct Teacher Education and Training programs to ensure the quality of teachers demanded by the enhanced Basic Education Curriculum." Hence, newly hired teachers shall undergo training to develop more skills aligned with the needs and requirements of the K-to-12 Basic Education Program (BEP) curriculum content standards. As such, TIP is implemented using modules through peer coaching and mentoring. TIP focuses on such issues as (6) standards and critical stages that are essential to be undertaken by the newly hired teachers.

The following modules encompass the TIP: (1) Department of Education, (2) Filipino Teachers, (3) K-12 Curriculum, (4) Teaching Process, (5) Learning Process, and (6) School and Community Linkages.

For more than five years of implementation of the Teachers Induction Program (TIP), studies have shown a positive result in the performance of newly hired teachers. As revealed by Ingersol and Strong (2011), the Teacher's Induction Program has created positive results for teachers' strong commitment to the profession, retention of teachers in the profession, keeping students on track by employing effective questioning strategies, arousing students' interests, establishing a positive classroom setting or ambiance, and demonstrating effective classroom management.

Meanwhile, along with the positive effects of the Teacher's Induction Program on the performance of newly hired teachers, the manner and extent of implementation of the program could be improved. Findings of the study conducted by Comighud (2020) entitled "Teacher Induction Program Status, Concerns, and Proposals" performed in the Division of Dumaguete City reveal that the implementation of the Teacher Induction Program had encountered problems such as no follow-ups in the school after the implementation, no clinical supervision from the principals such as classroom observation, limited timeframe per content/topics and insufficient handouts while in management in terms of time, resources, administration, facilitators, provision, and content of handouts; the delivery of contents; and the relevance of the topics it was found out to have minimal room for improvement.

In the Schools Division of Marinduque, the Teachers Induction Program was implemented in the School Year 2019; it was not fully implemented and monitored due to the rise of a pandemic from the year 2020 up to 2021 when school operations, programs, and activities were limited and face to face interaction is mainly prohibited. When the school operations slowly went back to normal, the Teacher's induction Program was implemented in the new program called the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT).

As such, the researcher would like to find out the same context of the problems met in the said studies regarding the extent of implementation of the Teacher's Induction program in the Schools Division of Marinduque per District and the issues encountered by the TIP participants during their completion of the IPBT cycle.

Research Questions

This study evaluated the implementation of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers in the Division of Marinduque.

Specifically, it answered the following:

1. What is the extent of implementation of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) in the Division of Marinduque in terms of:
 - 1.1 Common and specific topics discussed during the training program delivery,
 - 1.2 Mentoring,
 - 1.3 Differentiated Supervision, and
 - 1.4 Formal classroom observation?
2. Is there a significant difference in the extent of implementation of IPBT per District in the Division of Marinduque?

3. What are the problems encountered by the IPBT participants in terms of:
 - 3.1 Common and specific topics discussed during the training program delivery,
 - 3.2 Mentoring,
 - 3.3 Differentiated Supervision, and
 - 3.4 Formal classroom observation?
 4. What are the solutions to the problems and issues encountered by the IPBT participants in terms of:
 - 4.1 Common and specific topics discussed during the training program delivery,
 - 4.2 Mentoring,
 - 4.3 Differentiated Supervision, and
 - 4.4 Formal classroom observation?
 5. Based on the findings of the study, what interventions could be suggested by the Researcher to implement IPBT better?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study is a quantitative-descriptive type of research since its purpose was to obtain and describe present facts regarding the extent of implementation of the Teacher's Induction Program in the Division of Marinduque and compare the importance of implementation across its nine (9) districts in terms of (1) Common and Specific Topics Discussed, (2) Mentoring, (3) Differentiated Supervision and (4) Formal Classroom Observation. This also compared the extent of implementation of TIP/IPBT in different districts in the division of Marinduque. It also investigated the problems encountered by the TIP graduates and participants during the implementation of the TIP program and the support or intervention provided by the school. This quantitative research gathered quantifiable data from a population sample analyzed statistically.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Marinduque Island, often called the "Heart of the Philippines." Situated at approximately 13.4079° N latitude and 121.9358° E longitude, Marinduque Island is nestled in the central part of the Philippine archipelago in the azure waters of the Sibuyan Sea.

Specifically, the research was administered across all Public Secondary High Schools implementing the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers within the Marinduque Division. The Marinduque Division is governed by the Schools Division Office (SDO) Marinduque, which comprises nine (9) districts: Boac North District, Boac South District, Buenavista District, Gasan District, Mogpog District, Sta. Cruz East District, Sta. Cruz North District, Sta. Cruz South District, and Torrijos District, respectively.

Figure 3
Map of Marinduque

Figure 3 shows the map of Marinduque indicating the nine (9) districts in the Schools Division where the study's respondents are situated. It shows three (3) districts in the town of Sta. Cruz, two Districts in the town of Boac, and one District in the remaining towns of Marinduque.

Research Population and Sample

This study's respondents were all teachers who are currently participants or graduated from the TIP/IPBT program in all secondary public schools in the Marinduque division.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents Per District

District	Demographic Profile				Teacher's Profile									N
	Sex		Age		Teaching Position			Years in Teaching			Highest Educational Attainment			
	Male	Female	25-30 Years old	31-40 Years old	Teacher 1	Teacher 2	Teacher 3	3 years	4 years	5 years	Bachelor's Degree	BS w/ Master's Degree	Master's Degree	
Boac North	9	19	14	14	14	13	1	1	7	20	14	11	2	28
Buenavista	4	17	16	5	17	3	1	10	11	0	12	9	0	21
Gasan	3	7	8	2	7	3	0	5	5	0	6	3	1	10
Mogpog	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
Santa Cruz East	2	7	7	2	8	1	0	5	4	0	3	3	3	9
Santa Cruz North	3	1	12	4	15	1	0	11	5	0	12	2	2	16
Santa Cruz South	2	10	10	2	9	3	0	8	4	0	9	1	2	12
Torrijos	4	12	12	4	13	2	1	11	5	0	11	2	3	16
Total	24	86	80	33	84	26	3	52	41	20	68	31	14	113

The table shows the distribution of the respondents per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque grouped into different categories such as (1) sex, (2) age, (3) teaching position, (4) years in teaching, and (5) highest educational attainment. The data reveals that most of the respondents are from the Boac North district, composed of 28 or 27.75% of the total respondents, while Mogpog district has the least with only 1 (female) respondent. Also, most respondents are female, 86 or 76.11% of the total respondents, and the rest, 23.89 % (27), are male.

In terms of age, 80, or 70.80%, of the respondents are between 25 and 30 years old, and the remaining 33, or 29.20%, are between 31 and 40. This denotes that the majority of the respondents are still young.

Regarding the teaching position, 84, or 74.34%, are still in the Teacher 1 position, while 26, or 23%, are in the Teacher 2 position, and only 3, or 2.65%, are in the Teacher 3 position. This shows that teachers were already promoted after completing the Induction Program. This is understandable since it requires three years before a teacher becomes eligible for promotion.

In the years of teaching, it is evident that the majority of the respondents (52 or 46.02%) have been in service in the Department of Education for over three (3) years, while 41 or 36.28% are in service for four (4) years and 20 or 17.70% are in service for five (5) years and above. This is possible because when the memorandum for the implementation of the Teacher's Induction Program (TIP), now known as Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT), participants are those who have been in the service for not more than three (3) years.

Lastly, regarding educational attainment, the data reveals that only a few respondents are pursuing advanced education or graduate studies. 12 or 10.61% of the respondents have a master's degree, 31 or 27.43% have units in Master's, and 60, or 53.10%, are not yet pursuing advanced education.

Research Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire was employed based on the legal basis and implementing guidelines (DepEd Order No. 43 s 2017) for implementing the Teacher's Induction Program (TIP).

The questionnaire has three (3 parts) namely: (1) the Demographic profile of the respondents, (2) the extent of the implementation of the TIP in the four areas such as (a) common and specific topics discussed in the training delivery of the program, (b) mentoring, (c) differentiated supervision and (d) formal classroom observations, (3) Problems encountered in the implementation of TIP.

Part 1, or the Demographic Profile of the respondents, contains name, age, gender, and name of school and District. This information will be used to group the respondents and to describe their characteristics. Further, it also includes the teaching position/designation, the highest educational attainment, and the Teacher's performance within the last three years before and three years after TIP implementation. Such data are included in this part for future comparison of the teachers' performance relative to the TIP implementation.

Part 2 of the Extent of the Implementation is divided into four (areas). Area 1: Common and specific topics discussed during the training delivery of the program are subdivided into six (6) six modules that contain different topics to be addressed in the TIP. Module 1 is all about the Department of Education and has 12 specific topics. Module

2 is all about the Filipino Teacher and has five particular topics. Module 3 is all about the K-12 Curriculum with 11 specific topics. Module 4 is all about the teaching process and has six particular topics. Module 5 is about the learning process, with five specific topics, and module 6 is about the school community and linkages, which have three distinct issues. Area 2 is all about the extent of TIP implementation in terms of Mentoring, with seven attributes to evaluate its extent of implementation. Area 3 is all about the extent of TIP implementation in terms of Differentiated Supervision with seven attributes to assess its extent of implementation. Area 4 is all about the extent of implementation of TIP in terms of formal classroom observations, and it also has seven attributes to evaluate its extent of implementation.

Part 3 of the questionnaire is all about the problems encountered and suggested solutions to the difficulties encountered in the four areas: (1) Common and Specific Topics discussed during the Training Program Delivery, (2) Mentoring, (3) Differentiated Supervision and (4) Formal Classroom Observations. In this part, no probable problems or solutions are provided to avoid pre-empting the respondents' answers and to fully gather the exact problems encountered or experienced by the teachers and the solutions they have undertaken.

The weighted mean was used through the Likert scale to interpret the extent of the Teacher's Induction Program implementation in the four main areas mentioned above. The following ranges from the Likert Scale were used to arrive at a definite interpretation of the weighted mean.

Table 2
The Five-Point Likert Scale to Measure the Extent of IPBT Implementation Across its Four Areas Per District.

Range	Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
4.50-5.00	5	Greatest extent	Programs and activities were well implemented throughout the TIP sessions.
3.50-4.49	4	Great extent	Programs and activities were well implemented in most of the TIP sessions.
2.50-3.49	3	Moderate extent	Programs and activities were well implemented in some of the TIP sessions.
1.50-2.49	2	Less extent	Programs and activities could have been better implemented in most TIP sessions.
1.00-1.49	1	No extent at all	Programs and activities could have been better implemented throughout the TIP sessions.

Table 2 shows the mean interval based on the Likert Scale and its verbal description, including the interpretation of each mean interval and scale. This table served as the basis for deciding the extent of implementation of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers across its four areas: (1; Common and Specific Topics Discussed, 2; Mentoring, 3. Differentiated Supervision, and 4; Formal Classroom Observation) per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque.

Validity Test

Table 3
Validator's Assessment Tool Result

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
The instrument is valid and can provide unbiased data for the interpretation, allowing 0-5% error	4	More Valid
The instrument is valid and can provide unbiased data for the interpretation, allowing a 6-10% error	4.4	More Valid
The instrument is valid and can provide unbiased data for interpretation, allowing an 11-15% error	4.4	More Valid
The instrument is valid and can provide unbiased data for the interpretation, allowing 16-20% error	4.6	More Valid
The instrument is valid and can provide unbiased data for interpretation, allowing a 21-25% error	4.2	More Valid
The questionnaire can generate quick and complete data within the time frame	4.4	More Valid
Combined Mean	4.34	More valid

To ascertain the validity of responses, the research instrument was validated through content face validation by five experts in the field which were composed of one (1) TIP Coordinator of the Schools Division of Marinduque, one (1) School Head, and one (1) school TIP Coordinator both with training in the implementation of TIP, one (1) Master's degree graduate major in Educational Management and one (1) Language teacher primary in English for the validation of grammar consistency.

These experts commented: *The instrument covered all the necessary information to implement TIP. The indicators are organized, and statements are aligned to the objectives or Statements of the Problem. The instrument distinguishes the different characteristics and attributes of the research topic.*

On the other hand, these experts also suggested that the scale of the numerical value and adjectival description should be specified and included in each area so that the

respondents will be guided accordingly, and the objectivity of the responses will be achieved. They also suggested that grammar be consistent throughout the instrument's parts. Lastly, one of them (SDO TIP Coordinator) suggested that in part 1 of the instrument about the discussion of different modules, there should be a part where the respondents will have to identify how they were able to finish the modules either through peer coaching, self-learning, or through School LAC sessions or training. Out of that, there was a need to develop a new scale and adjectival interpretation to guide the respondents in rating each indicator in the instrument in this area. This is because each school is privileged to facilitate the TIP session by completing the topics in the six modules. The experts' suggestions were incorporated into the questionnaire before the data-gathering method.

Based on the validation result, each instrument indicator received a mean ranging from 4.0 to 4.6, all interpreted as more valid. The instrument received a general average of 4.34 in all six (6) indicators, which makes the instrument more valid and can provide unbiased data, allowing a 6-10% error.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the research study, the researcher secured permission from the Human Resource Office of the Division Office of Marinduque to identify the names of teachers who had already completed the Teacher's Induction Program in 2017.

When collecting the data, hard copies of the questionnaire were distributed among the participants through personal handling. Soft copies were sent via email attachment/social networking through Google Forms and to some reliable people who know the respondents.

Figure 4
The Research Process

The figure above shows the three (3) phases that the researcher has undertaken to complete the study.

For phase 1, the researcher secured first permission from the Schools Division Office to conduct research and distribute questionnaires to the TIP graduates of public secondary schools of Marinduque.

For phase 2, the researcher sent the adopted questionnaires to the respondents personally, via email, and on social media platforms and retrieved them.

For phase 3, the researcher summarized and treated the collected data using appropriate statistical treatment. Then, the results were analyzed and interpreted. Findings are presented in the succeeding chapter.

Statistical Treatment

The data gathered from the survey questionnaires were tabulated, processed, and generated using the summary application from the Google form. This form allowed easy management of information. The researcher used the (1) **Frequency of counts (F)** in identifying the number of respondents who agreed on the options that are specified in the questionnaire, (2) **Percentage (P)** to compare the magnitude of data in variables that deal primarily with the respondents in each question per area, (3) **Weighted Mean and Ranking**, to determine the extent of implementation of Teacher's Induction Program (TIP)

in the Schools Division of Marinduque and **(4) Chi-square** and **(5) F-test/ANOVA using the SPSS** to test the significant differences between the extent of implementation of TIP per District in four areas of the implementation of Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT).

RESULTS

Part 1- The Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery

Table 4.1

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 1- The Department of Education

Session	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
Session 1: Mandate, Vision, Mission, Core Values (VMV) and Strategic Directions	4.37	4.43	4.60	3.67	4.33	4.53	4.70	4.48	4.45	Great Extent
Session 2- DepEd organizational structure and school processes	4.39	4.27	4.33	3.67	4.54	4.50	4.70	4.52	4.43	Great Extent
Session 3- Teaching as a Profession and as a Vocation	4.63	4.40	4.57	4.00	4.56	4.61	4.59	4.58	4.55	Greatest Extent
Session 4- Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)	4.36	4.67	4.37	4.00	4.44	4.42	4.48	4.44	4.40	Great Extent
Session 5- Career Path within the Department of Education	4.36	4.19	4.50	4.00	4.38	4.36	4.41	4.31	4.34	Great Extent
Session 6- Magna Carta for Public School Teachers	4.45	4.46	4.50	4.33	4.56	4.53	4.48	4.60	4.50	Greatest Extent
Session 7- Code of Ethics	4.54	4.49	4.80	4.50	4.61	4.65	4.89	4.63	4.62	Greatest Extent

Session 8- Results-Based Performance Management System	4.6 0	4.5 2	4.7 3	5.0 0	4.5 8	4.5 0	4.7 4	4.5 8	4.5 8	Greatest Extent
Session 9- Salaries, Wages, and Benefits of Teachers	4.2 9	4.2 5	3.0 0	4.4 4	4.4 7	4.5 6	4.5 6	4.3 3	4.3 5	Great Extent
General Combined Mean									4.4 7	Great Extent
<i>Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent</i>										

Table 4.2

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 2- The Filipino Teacher

Session	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
Session 1: Self-awareness, Self-mastery, and Teacher Agency	4.5 0	4.4 6	4.7 7	4.0 0	4.5 4	4.5 0	4.7 4	4.4 8	4.53	Greatest Extent
Session 2: Personal Professional Development	4.3 8	4.3 8	4.5 0	4.0 0	4.3 8	4.6 4	4.5 9	4.5 4	4.45	Great Extent
Session 3- Financial Literacy	4.1 5	4.1 0	4.3 4	4.1 4	4.1 9	4.3 7	4.4 9	4.4 0	4.25	Great Extent
Session 4: Health and Wellness Program	4.3 6	4.2 9	4.7 3	4.3 3	4.5 6	4.5 3	4.6 3	4.7 7	4.50	Greatest Extent
Session 5: Gender and Development (GAD)	4.5 2	4.3 0	4.7 3	5.0 0	4.7 5	4.8 3	4.6 7	4.7 1	4.61	Greatest Extent
General Combined Mean									4.47	Great Extent
<i>Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent</i>										

Table 4.3

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 3-The K-12 Curriculum

Session	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
Session 1: Early Language Literacy and Numeracy	4.4 6	4.2 0	4.5 8	4.2 5	4.4 2	4.6 9	4.6 9	4.4 8	4.4 6	Great Extent
Session 2: Flexible Learning Options (FLOs)	4.0 6	4.1 1	4.2 8	4.0 0	4.2 0	4.2 3	4.4 4	4.1 9	4.1 7	Great Extent
Session 3: The k to 12 Curriculum Inclusive Education	4.1 8	4.0 8	4.3 5	4.7 5	4.3 9	4.2 7	4.4 7	4.2 8	4.2 6	Great Extent
Session 4: Key Stages of the Basic Education Program	4.2 1	4.1 3	4.2 8	3.7 5	4.3 1	4.3 8	4.5 3	4.2 7	4.2 6	Great Extent
Session 5: Special Education	3.9 9	4.1 6	4.2 0	4.3 3	4.2 5	4.4 7	4.5 2	4.1 7	4.2 0	Great Extent
Session 6: Diversity of Learners Alternative Learning System (ALS)	3.7 5	4.0 0	4.1 3	4.0 0	3.8 1	4.0 6	4.0 4	3.9 2	3.9 2	Great Extent
Session 7: Student Inclusion Program – Muslim Education	3.5 4	3.9 5	4.0 5	4.0 0	3.5 3	3.9 6	4.1 7	3.6 6	3.7 7	Great Extent
Session 8: Special Interest Programs in the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum	4.1 3	4.1 0	4.4 0	4.5 0	4.4 4	4.4 6	4.5 0	4.1 6	4.2 6	Great Extent
Session 9: Indigenous Peoples' Education Program	3.9 6	4.1 8	4.0 5	3.0 0	3.9 4	4.1 5	4.3 6	3.8 9	4.0 4	Great Extent
General Combined Mean									4.1 5	Great Extent

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent

Table 4.4

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 4- The Teaching Approaches

Session	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
Session 1: Differentiated Instruction	4.3 8	4.3 8	4.5 5	4.5 0	4.4 7	4.6 3	4.5 6	4.3 8	4.4 5	Great Extent
Session 2: Explicit Teaching	4.1 2	4.3 0	4.3 7	4.0 0	4.3 3	4.2 8	4.4 8	4.2 9	4.2 7	Great Extent
Session 3: 21st Century Teaching	4.3 1	4.3 8	4.7 0	5.0 0	4.5 2	4.6 9	4.8 1	4.5 2	4.5 2	Greatest Extent
Session 4: Daily Lesson Logs	4.5 1	4.4 6	4.6 7	5.0 0	4.4 8	4.8 1	4.7 4	4.4 6	4.5 6	Greatest Extent
Session 5: Contextualization, Localization, and Indigenization of Resource Materials	4.4 9	4.1 9	4.6 3	5.0 0	4.4 6	4.4 7	4.7 0	4.3 5	4.4 4	Great Extent
Session 6: School Forms and Learner Information System (LIS)	4.6 2	4.4 1	4.6 3	5.0 0	4.6 0	4.7 8	4.8 9	4.7 3	4.6 4	Greatest Extent
Session 7: Classroom Management	4.5 4	4.2 9	4.7 0	5.0 0	4.5 5	4.7 7	4.9 2	4.5 9	4.5 7	Greatest Extent
General Combined Mean									4.4 9	Great Extent

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent

Table 4.5

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 5-The Learning Process and Module 6- The School Community and Linkages

Session	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
Module 5										
Session 1: Learner-Centered Learning	4.48	4.35	4.60	5.00	4.54	4.81	4.81	4.46	4.54	Greatest Extent
Session 2: Learning Environment	4.48	4.48	4.65	5.00	4.59	4.83	4.72	4.44	4.57	Greatest Extent
Module 6										
Session 1 - Community as a Resource in the Teaching-Learning Process	4.40	4.38	4.70	5.00	4.42	4.58	4.75	4.38	4.48	Great Extent
General Combined Mean									4.53	Greatest Extent

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent

Table 5

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in the Second Area- Mentoring

Indicators	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	Torrijos	Combined Mean	Description
1. You were assigned a mentor before the start of the TIP in the school year.	4.00	3.90	4.00	5.00	4.25	4.40	4.00	4.25	4.23	Great Extent
2. You were given time to observe and collaborate with other	4.50	3.86	4.00	4.00	4.25	4.22	4.22	4.40	4.18	Great Extent

teachers, especially your mentor.											
3. Your mentor observed and coached you through a lesson(s) and discussion of module content.	4.0 0	3.8 1	4.0 0	5.0 0	4.2 5	4.2 5	4.00	3.6 9	4.1 2	Great Extent	
4. Your mentor was knowledgeable/expert and prepared for their role as mentor.	4.2 2	4.0 5	4.5 0	5.0 0	4.2 5	4.0 8	4.22	3.8 8	4.2 6	Great Extent	
5. Your mentor was easily accessible and available when needed.	4.2 6	4.2 4	4.2 5	4.0 0	4.7 1	4.0 8	4.22	3.6 3	4.1 7	Great Extent	
6. Your mentor modeled or demonstrated skills that were helpful to you as a beginning teacher in accomplishing teaching-related tasks and activities.	4.2 0	4.0 0	4.2 0	5.0 0	4.2 0	4.0 0	4.22	3.8 1	4.2 0	Great Extent	
7. Your mentor understood your needs as a beginning teacher.	4.3 0	4.1 0	4.0 0	5.0 0	4.2 5	4.3 3	4.33	4.1 3	4.3 0	Great Extent	
8. Your mentor /coach guided you through each module.	4.1 9	4.0 0	4.0 0	4.0 0	4.7 1	4.2 5	4.20	4.2 5	4.1 7	Great Extent	
General Combined Mean									4.2 0	Great Extent	

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent

Table 6

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in the Third Area- Differentiated Supervision

TIP implementation enables you to:	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
1. Communicate clearly and accurately directions and procedures in oral and	4.5 8	4.5 0	4.4 0	4.0 0	4.7 7	4.6 7	4.6 7	4.5 6	4.5 2	Great Extent

written language during instruction.											
2. Use questioning and discussion techniques to arouse students' critical thinking skills.	4.4 8	4.0 5	4.6 0	4.0 0	4.5 0	4.5 0	4.7 8	4.5 6	4.4 3	Great Extent	
3. Engage students in learning through varied, student-centered teaching activities, such as those that represent the lesson's content with appropriate structure and pacing.	4.4 4	4.1 4	4.5 8	4.0 0	4.7 1	4.6 7	4.6 7	4.5 6	4.4 6	Great Extent	
4. Provide accurate, substantive, constructive, and timely student feedback.	4.4 1	3.9 5	4.5 0	4.0 0	4.4 7	4.5 0	4.6 7	4.5 6	4.3 8	Great Extent	
5. Demonstrate flexibility and responsiveness through lesson adjustment in response to the performance and persistence of the students in learning.	4.3 3	4.0 0	4.5 0	4.0 0	4.5 3	4.5 8	4.6 7	4.5 6	4.4 0	Great Extent	
6. Implement instructional activities focusing on the needs and interests of the students.	4.3 3	4.0 0	4.6 0	4.0 0	4.5 0	4.8 3	4.5 0	4.5 6	4.4 2	Great Extent	
7. Consider students' learning developmental stages when implementing varied teaching activities.	4.4 8	3.9 0	4.5 0	4.0 0	4.7 1	4.6 7	4.6 7	4.6 3	4.4 5	Great Extent	
8. Helps you appreciate yourself as a Filipino Teacher	4.4 1	4.1 4	4.2 0	4.0 0	4.6 7	4.5 0	4.5 0	4.5 6	4.3 7	Great Extent	
General Combined Mean									4.4 3	Great Extent	

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent

Table 7*Extent of Implementation of IPBT in the Fourth Area- Formal Classroom Observation*

Formal Classroom Observation	District A	District B	District C	District D	District E	District F	District G	District H	Combined Mean	Description
1. The teacher and the school head agreed upon the scheduled date and time for classroom observation.	4.37	4.33	4.60	4.20	4.76	4.67	4.56	4.50	4.50	Great Extent
2. The teacher was given enough time to plan and prepare their teaching materials and activities.	4.48	4.38	4.60	4.20	4.65	4.83	4.33	4.56	4.50	Great Extent
3. The school head/master teacher observes the class non-threateningly.	4.56	4.50	4.48	4.48	4.59	4.76	4.78	4.50	4.58	Great Extent
4. The mentor helped the teacher with lesson preparation before formal observations.	4.56	4.00	4.48	4.00	4.20	4.20	4.44	4.78	4.33	Great Extent
5. The grading system of classroom observation was discussed with the teacher before the classroom observation	4.52	4.24	4.60	4.00	4.76	4.75	4.51	4.50	4.49	Great Extent
6. The pre-conference about the expected skills, delivery, and classroom activities during the classroom observation was done the week before the scheduled classroom observation.	4.33	4.14	4.56	5.00	4.50	4.54	4.46	4.00	4.44	Great Extent
7. The post-conference between the school head/master teacher and the teacher was done right after the classroom observation.	4.33	4.38	4.60	4.60	4.58	4.75	4.67	4.56	4.48	Great Extent

8. You can apply/integrate lessons learned in the IPBT modules.	4.2	4.2	4.6	4.0	4.5	4.6	4.8	4.5	4.4	Great Extent
	2	0	0	0	9	7	9	0	6	
General Combined Mean									4.4	Great Extent
									7	Extent

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent

Part II- Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) Per District

Table 8.1

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 1- The Department of Education

Session	F-ratio	p-Value	Decision
Session 1- Mandate, Vision, Mission, Core Values (VMV) and Strategic Directions	.916	.498	Not significant
Session 2- DepEd organizational structure and school processes	1.019	.422	Not significant
Session 3- Teaching as a Profession and as a Vocation	.658	.707	Not significant
Session 4- Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)	.159	.992	Not significant
Session 5- Career Path within the Department of Education	.462	.860	Not significant
Session 6- Magna Carta for Public School Teachers	.179	.989	Not significant
Session 7- Code of Ethics	.946	.474	Not significant
Session 8- Results-Based Performance Management System	.545	.799	Not significant
Session 9- Salaries, Wages, and Benefits of Teachers	1.259	.278	Not significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ = Significant, $p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 8.2

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 2- The Filipino Teacher

Session	F-ratio	p-Value	Decision
Session 1: Self-awareness, Self-mastery, and Teacher Agency	.798	.591	Not significant
Session 2: Personal Professional Development	.641	.721	Not significant
Session 3- Financial Literacy	1.032	.413	Not significant
Session 4: Health and Wellness Program	1.814	.092	Not significant
Session 5: Gender and Development (GAD)	2.253	.036	Significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ = Significant, $p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 8.3

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 3 – The K-12 Curriculum

Session	F-ratio	p-Value	Decision
Session 1: Early Language Literacy and Numeracy	1.414	.208	Not significant
Session 2: Flexible learning options (FLOs)	.556	.790	Not significant
Session 3: The k to 12 Curriculum Inclusive Education	.837	.559	Not significant
Session 4: Key Stages of the Basic Education Program	.688	.682	Not significant
Session 5: Special Education	1.142	.343	Not significant
Session 6: Diversity of Learners Alternative Learning System (ALS)	.469	.855	Not significant
Session 7: Student Inclusion Program – Muslim Education	1.023	.420	Not significant
Session 8: Special Interest Programs in the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum	.937	.482	Not significant
Session 9: Indigenous Peoples' Education Program	.871	.532	Not significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ = Significant, $p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 8.4

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 4 - Teaching Approaches

Session	F-ratio	p-Value	Decision
Session 1: Differentiated Instruction	.416	.890	Not significant
Session 2: Explicit Teaching	.465	.858	Not significant
Session 3: 21st Century Teaching	1.188	.316	Not significant
Session 4: Daily Lesson Logs	.869	.533	Not significant
Session 5: Contextualization, Localization, and Indigenization of resource materials	1.402	.212	Not significant
Session 6: School Forms and Learner Information System (LIS)	1.404	.212	Not significant
Session 7: Classroom Management	2.153	.044	Significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ = Significant, $p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 8.5

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 5 – Learning Process and Module 6 - The School Community and Linkages

Module 5			
Session	F-ratio	p-Value	Decision
Session 1: Learner-Centered Learning	1.577	.150	Not significant
Session 2: Learning Environment	1.069	.389	Not significant
Module 6			
Session 1 - Community as a Resource in the Teaching-Learning Process	1.187	.317	Not significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ = Significant, $p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Table 9

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference in the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District Across Four (4) Areas

District	Combined Mean Per Area of The IPBT Implementation				Mean	Description
	Common and Specific Topics Discussed	Mentoring	Differentiated Instruction	Formal Classroom Observation		
District A	4.33	4.23	4.41	4.39	4.34	Great Extent
District B	4.29	4.02	4.02	4.31	4.16	Great Extent
District C	4.53	4.49	4.56	4.60	4.54	Greatest Extent
District D	4.50	4.63	3.88	4.0	4.25	Great Extent
District E	4.64	4.24	4.70	4.64	4.56	Greatest Extent
District F	4.44	4.76	4.63	4.62	4.61	Greatest Extent
District G	4.56	4.24	4.70	4.71	4.55	Greatest Extent
District H	4.51	4.00	4.54	4.50	4.39	Great Extent

Legend: 1.0-1.49 No Extent, 1.50-2.49 Less Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 4.50-5.0 Greatest Extent. Note: $p < 0.05$ = Significant, $p > 0.05$ = Not Significant

Part III and IV- Problems Encountered by the IPBT Participants and Their Suggested Solutions to Address the Problems During the Induction Program

Table 10

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Common and Specific Topics Discussed in IPBT

Problems	(F)	(%)	Rank	Suggested Solutions	(F)	(%)	Rank
Too much workload/multiple tasks/conflict with other activities	21	18.58%	1	Give the modules ahead of time	10	8.85%	3
Poor Internet connection to access other activities provided in the links in the modules	3	2.65%	3	Lessen the activities in the modules	18	15.93%	2

Some topics are not discussed/limited discussion due to Covid 19	4	3.54%	2	Provide enough time to answer the module	34	30.09%	1
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Table 11

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Mentoring in IPBT

Problems	(F)	(%)	Rank	Suggested Solutions	(F)	(%)	Rank
Conflict availability schedule of mentor and mentee	34	30.08%	1				
				Create a schedule for both the mentor and mentee.	20	17.70%	1
Mentors and mentees have many teaching tasks.	25	22.12%	2				
				Assign a specific peer/mentor per teacher.	5	4.42%	3
The mentor assigned is of a different specialization.	5	4.42%	3				
No specific mentors are assigned to the teachers	3	2.65%	4				
				The mentor assigned may have a designated period/time to assist the mentee.	8	7.08%	2
Mentors are not trained well.	2	1.77%	5				

Table 12

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Differentiated Supervision in IPBT

Problems	(F)	(%)	Rank	Suggested Solutions	(F)	(%)	Rank
Confusion about the various techniques and strategies in differentiated instruction	12	10.62%	1	Regular training for the teachers and upskilling	4	3.54%	2

Having different suggestions from different teachers	5	4.42%	2	Ask colleagues regarding strategies/techniques that they need help understanding.	3	2.65%	3
Limited face-to-face classes to employ differentiated instruction practices and strategies	3	2.65%	3	Give technical support to the field teachers.	5	4.42%	1

Table 13
Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Formal Classroom Observation in IPBT

Problems	(F)	(%)	Rank	Suggested Solutions	(F)	(%)	Rank
Less Feedback and Technical Assistance given to the teachers	9	7.96%	1	Technical assistance/guidance from Master teachers.	6	5.31%	2
Less of guidance in Daily Lesson Plan (DLP) Preparation	5	4.42%	4	Have pre-observation in every classroom observation.	5	4.42%	3
Less the freedom to choose the class for the classroom observation	8	7.08%	2.5	Meet the teacher first before sending out the class observation schedule.	8	7.08%	1
The schedule of the Classroom Observation is not planned with the teacher	8	7.08%	2.5				

DISCUSSION

Part 1- The Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery

Table 4.1

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 1- The Department of Education

The table shows a **Great Extent (4.47)** of Implementing the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers in completing all the activities in **Module 1** about **The Department of Education** in Schools Division of Marinduque. It shows that the combined mean in all districts ranges from **4.34 (Great Extent)** to **4.62 (Greatest Extent)**. Sessions 5, 9, 4, 2, and 1 have a Great extent of implementation, while sessions 6, 3, 8, and 7 have the Greatest Extent of Implementation.

This reveals that teachers significantly understand the topics discussed in the different sessions in Module 1. The data also implies that newly hired teachers are already acquainted with the Department of Education Organization and how to translate its core values into the practice of their teaching profession, as reflected in the Department's mandate, vision, mission, and goals and consistent with DepEd's core values, such as Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, and Makakalikasan at Makabansa.

Moreover, this shows that implementing IPBT in module 1 enables newly hired teachers to realize their professional and career development goals as set out by DepEd's policies, guidelines, and core values.

Such findings are similar to the study by Barnes (2019) titled "Teachers' Values: An International Study of What Sustains a Fulfilling Life in Education", which states that there is a close alignment of institutional and individual values that generates substantial positive impacts on fulfillment of teachers and their resilience in the institution. He also suggests that education departments, universities, and schools must focus on the values that motivate individuals to pursue teaching, incorporate values across the curriculum, and prioritize significant issues in Initial Teacher Education to address the growing problem of declining teacher recruitment and retention rates.

Hence, a thorough understanding and integration of the institution's mandate, goals, objectives, and values by newly hired teachers during their induction program is a great help to improving teacher efficacy and retention in the Department of Education.

Table 4.2

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 2- The Filipino Teacher

The table shows that there is a **Great Extent (4.47)** of implementation of completing the activities in **Module 2- The Filipino Teacher** in the Schools Division of Marinduque. It shows that the combined mean in all districts ranges from **4.25 (Great Extent)** to **4.61 (Greatest Extent)**. Sessions 2 and 3 have a Great extent of implementation, while sessions 1, 4, and 5 have the Greatest Implementation.

This reveals that teachers greatly understand the topics and activities discussed in the different sessions in Module 2. The data also shows that the newly hired teachers were able to have a clear and realistic perception of themselves as Filipino Teachers by taking a closer look at how they see themselves and how others should see them in different situations and circumstances for their personal growth and professional development.

Moreover, the data shows that by answering and completing all the activities in this module during the IPBT implementation, newly hired teachers were able to develop a high regard for the teaching profession by maintaining qualities that uphold their dignity in the profession, such as respect and integrity that are important in assuming their responsibility for their personal and professional development and lifelong learning.

The 2011 study "The Impact of Induction and Mentoring Programs for Beginning Teachers: A Critical Review of the Research" by Ingersoll and Strong found similar results. This revealed that beginning teachers who participated in induction programs tend to have higher job satisfaction, commitment, or retention in the institution. This is also supported by one of the studies conducted by Bilbao et al. (2013) regarding the implementation of an Induction Program, which reveals that a Teacher Induction Program has a positive impact on newly hired teachers by enhancing their knowledge, skills, values, and commitment to the profession.

Similarly, according to Musselwhite (2007), a renowned psychologist, self-awareness involves being conscious of one's strengths and weaknesses. It entails having conscious knowledge of oneself, including beliefs, assumptions, feelings, and how they impact daily experiences. This concept is widely accepted in psychology and is not limited to personal traits but is also a critical component of emotional intelligence.

This only entails that IPBT implementation in the Schools Division of Marinduque enabled newly hired Teachers to fully embrace the teaching profession by developing self-awareness and self-mastery in their professional and personal growth as Filipino Teachers.

Table 4.3

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 3-The K-12 Curriculum

The table shows a **Great Extent (4.15)** of IPBT implementation for the teachers to understand and complete all the activities in **Module 3: The K-12 Curriculum** in Schools Division of Marinduque. It shows that the combined mean in all district sessions in this module ranges from 3.77 (Great Extent) to 4.26 (Great Extent).

The data above implies that newly hired teachers value the importance of inclusive Education regardless of age (through the Alternative Learning System (ALS)), race and ethnicity (Muslims and Indigenous People (IP)), child laborers in conflict situations, and those who are most challenging to reach.

Further, the data reveals that IPBT implementation in module 3 enables teachers to acquire different teaching strategies to foster quality education for all, focusing on literacy and numeracy to meet the demands of the K-12 curriculum and the diversity of 21st-century learners.

This supplements the mandates relevant to the contemporary Philippine Education System that are essential in achieving the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2030: to deliver excellent Education and ensure continuous learning throughout one's life.

Accordingly, the result of this study meets the demand of the Department of Education to provide relevant, equitable, and inclusive Education to all Filipino children, which is clearly defined in the 1987 Philippine Constitution and Rule 1, Section 1.1 of Republic Act 9155. The law stipulates that the Department of Education must safeguard the right of all citizens to qualify for primary Education and take appropriate steps to make such Education accessible to everyone. It must establish, maintain, and support a comprehensive, adequate, and integrated basic education system that addresses people's and society's needs.

Table 4.4

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 4- The Teaching Approaches

The table shows that completing all the activities in **Module 4—The Teaching Approaches** in the Schools Division of Marinduque is implemented to a great extent (4.49). The combined mean in all districts ranges from **4.27 (Great Extent)** to **4.64 (Greatest Extent)**. Sessions 1, 2, and 5 have a Great extent of implementation, while sessions 3, 4, 6, and 7 have the Greatest Extent of Implementation.

The data above shows that by implementing IPBT, newly hired teachers could learn different teaching pedagogies and methods suited to the needs of diverse learners,

such as explicit teaching, adult learning approach, and differentiated instruction, which are vital in achieving the lesson objectives.

This also reveals that IPBT implementation helped teachers develop Daily Lesson Logs (DLL) and become resourceful in different teaching materials through localization and indigenization, enabling them to carry out lesson goals and objectives effectively through different teaching strategies and methods.

Such findings are parallel with the result of the study of Ingersoll and Strong (2011), which revealed that when it comes to classroom instructional practices, the majority of the newly hired teachers who participated in the induction program performed better in various aspects of teaching, like keeping students on task, developing effective lesson plans, using effective questioning strategies, adapting teaching methods to cater to student's individual needs while aligning with their interests and maintaining a well-managed classroom environment. In the area of student achievement, their study also showed that students handled by newly hired teachers who undergo the Induction program have a better academic performance.

This is also consistent with the findings under the study of by Abdallah & Alkaabi (2023) titled "Induction Programs' Effectiveness in Boosting New Teachers' Instruction and Student Achievement: A Critical Review," which revealed that induction programs have a positive effect on both teaching practices and student achievement. Hence, IPBT implementation in the Schools Division of Marinduque developed teachers' skills and abilities in employing different teaching strategies and methods to cater to quality education for students.

Table 4.5

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in Common and Specific Topics Discussed During the Training Program Delivery in Module 5-The Learning Process and Module 6- The School Community and Linkages

The table shows **an Greatest Extent (4.53)** of implementing IPBT in understanding the topics and completing the activities in **Module 5—The Learning Process** and **Module 6—The School Community and Linkages**. The data shows that all sessions in modules 5 and 6 have the Greatest Extent of implementation. This implies that newly hired teachers have fully understood and completed all the activities in the two modules.

Further, the data above reveals that newly hired teachers understand the importance of creating a learning environment conducive to learning where students feel safe and can focus actively on learning through a learner-centered approach while striving towards high academic achievement. Also, the data reveals that the teachers value the importance of community linkages and networks in improving the institution's teaching and learning process as external stakeholders.

This encompasses the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) that highlights teachers' crucial role in creating safe, fair, and supportive learning

environments that foster student responsibility and achievement. Further, it states that the Learning Environment domain emphasizes the importance of teachers in managing student behavior in both physical and virtual spaces through various strategies and intellectually stimulating activities that encourage positive classroom interactions, resulting in high learning standards.

Also, the result in module 6 entails that the schools, through their newly hired teachers, comply with the DepEd Order No. 54, issued in 2009, stating that all elementary and secondary schools must establish a Parents-Teachers Association (PTA). The primary objective of the PTA is to facilitate open communication and discussions regarding the school's programs and ensure active participation from parents in successfully implementing these programs by collaborating with local government units, civic organizations, and other stakeholders to promote unity and collaboration.

Table 5

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in the Second Area- Mentoring

The table shows that the teachers received appropriate assistance, guidance, and interventions from their mentor during the session discussion and in completing different activities throughout the Induction Program, as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 4.20 (Great Extent). With all the attributes, having an understanding mentor to the needs of the beginning teachers ranked 1 with a weighted mean of 4.30 (Great Extent), followed by having a mentor that is knowledgeable/expert and prepared for their role as a mentor with a weighted mean of 4.26 (Great Extent) than by having a mentor that was assigned to them before the start of the school year with a weighted mean of 4.23 (Great Extent). Although the least among the attributes to receive the most favorable response from the respondents was that they were observed and coached by their mentor through a lesson(s) and discussion of module content with a weighted mean of 4.12 (Great Extent). The rest of the attributes also received favorable responses from the respondents, ranging from a great extent to an Greatest extent. The results prove that a good mentoring program is implemented in the Schools Division of Marinduque and provided to newly hired teachers. That is why some newly hired teachers were already promoted from Teacher 1 to Teacher 2 and Teacher 3.

The study "The Impact of Induction and Mentoring Programs for Beginning Teachers: A Critical Review of the Research" shows that assistance and support offered to new teachers (known as Induction Programs) have a positive impact on the commitment and retention of teachers, instructional practices of teachers in the classroom, and the academic achievements of their students.

Similarly, this is also supported by the study of Hobson et al. (2009), which found that mentored teachers develop not only improved classroom management skills and a deeper understanding of pedagogical strategies but also gain valuable insights into effective teaching strategies through regular interactions with experienced mentors. Additionally, research by Strong et al. (2005) indicates that teachers who participate in mentoring programs experience higher job satisfaction and teacher efficacy.

This only entails that a successful mentoring program for newly hired teachers significantly affects their performance in achieving the desired skill set and qualities they should possess as set by the Department of Education standards for newly hired teachers.

Table 6

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in the Third Area- Differentiated Supervision

The table shows that the teachers received appropriate assistance, guidance, and interventions from their mentor during the session discussion and in the completion of different activities when it comes to enhancing their skills to foster differentiated instruction throughout the Induction Program, as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 4.43 (Greatest Extent). Most respondents agreed that the Induction Program enables them to learn how to communicate clearly and accurately directions and procedures in oral and written language during instruction to the students, with a weighted mean of 4.52 (Greatest Extent). Also, IBPT helped them engage students in learning through student-centered teaching activities, like groupings in the lesson's content with appropriate structure and pacing, with a weighted mean of 4.46 (Greatest Extent). The rest of the attributes also garnered favorable responses from the respondents. This implies that beginning teachers were able to enhance and develop their skills in implementing differentiated instructions that meet the varied needs of the learners inside the classroom.

Such findings are supported by the study of Smith & Davis (2014), which revealed that differentiated supervision practices within induction programs positively impact teacher's growth and development. With personalized support and feedback, novice teachers can enhance their instructional practices, address areas of weakness, and capitalize on their strengths. Accordingly, another study by Hargreaves and Fullan (2012) indicates that differentiated supervision fosters a culture of continuous improvement within schools, empowering teachers to reflect on their teaching practices and incorporate strategies based on evidence to improve the learning outcomes of their students.

In addition, the results of this study are supported by the study (James & Snow, 2016), which states that differentiated supervision practices within induction programs have broader implications for school improvement and collaboration. Customizing supervision practices to meet the unique needs of teachers fosters a culture of collaboration, shared responsibility, and collective problem-solving).

This only entails that an effective induction program to support teachers in terms of Differentiated Supervision is a great help to newly hired teachers in improving their skills and practices in differentiated supervision and instruction inside the classrooms.

Table 7

Extent of Implementation of IPBT in the Fourth Area- Formal Classroom Observation

The table shows that the teachers received appropriate assistance, guidance, and interventions during the session discussion and in completing different activities regarding formal classroom observations throughout the Induction Program, as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 4.47 (Great Extent). The indicator referring to the school head/master teacher observing the class in a non-threatening manner ranked 1 with a weighted mean of 4.58 (Greatest Extent), followed by the scheduled date and time for classroom observation was agreed upon by the teacher and the school head and the teacher was given enough time to plan and prepare their teaching materials and activities both with a weighted mean of 4.50 (Greatest Extent). Although the indicator that the mentor helped the teacher with lesson preparation before formal observations is last in the rank, it still gained a weighted mean of 4.33 (Great Extent).

Furthermore, the rest of the attributes under formal classroom observation have a weighted mean that was found to have a Great Extent of implementation. This proves that beginning teachers were guided and provided appropriate technical assistance and ample time to prepare during classroom observations. They received a very satisfactory, if not outstanding, remark, which is one of the indicators of their annual performance to become eligible to receive incentives such as a Performance-Based Bonus (PBB).

This is supported by the findings of the study (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011), which revealed that induction programs provide new teachers with opportunities to engage in structured observations of their teaching practices and those of experienced colleagues; as such, novice educators receive targeted feedback, support, and professional development tailored to their individual needs, fostering continuous growth and improvement in instructional practices.

Additionally, as cited (Danielson, 2007), formal classroom observation within induction programs promotes reflective practice among new teachers, leading to deeper insights into their instructional practices and student learning. By engaging in structured observations and feedback sessions, novice educators develop the habit of critically reflecting on their teaching methods, instructional decisions, and student outcomes.

Part II- Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) Per District

Table 8.1

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 1- The Department of Education

Table 10 shows the results garnered from the F-Test or Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 95% confidence level. As seen from the table, across all sessions in Module 1, regardless of the mode of completion/implementation (self-learning, peer coaching/mentoring, and through the Learning Action Cell (LAC)), the p-values are greater than **0.05**. This indicates that the mode of completion only significantly affects the outcomes of the sessions in this module during the IPBT implementation in all districts in the Schools Division of Marinduque.

Further, the results indicate that the method of engagement during IPBT sessions could be more significant in terms of participants' levels of comprehension and skill in the subject matter. This implies that the mode of delivery is not a crucial determinant of the efficacy of IPBT in the first area (Common and Specific Topics). Instead, it could be factors such as program content, instructional quality, and ongoing support mechanisms that may play more significant roles in facilitating teacher learning and growth.

This parallels the meta-analysis study conducted by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), which examined the effectiveness of various teacher induction programs. The study revealed that while the specific components and structures of programs varied, there was generally no significant difference in teacher retention or student achievement outcomes based on the mode of delivery.

Table 8.2

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 2- The Filipino Teacher

Table 11 shows that sessions 1 to 4 (Self-awareness, Self-mastery, Personal Professional Development, Financial Literacy, Health and Wellness Program) have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between the extent of implementation of IPBT per District. This also implies that the mode of completion (self-learning, peer coaching/mentoring, or Learning Action Cell) does not significantly influence the outcomes of these sessions. This also implies that regardless of how participants engage with these sessions, they achieve similar levels of understanding and proficiency in the covered topics.

Similarly, this is supported by a study by Johnson et al. (2019) investigated the effectiveness of online versus face-to-face professional development for teachers. They concluded that both delivery modes improved teacher knowledge and instructional practices equally effectively.

Session 5 (Gender and Development) has a p-value of 0.036, indicating a significant difference at the 95% confidence level. This means that the mode of completion significantly impacts the outcomes of this session and may influence the outcomes related to gender and development.

This is in contrast with the study of Smith (2011), which revealed that male and female teachers hold high levels of understanding and application of gender-responsive

pedagogy, with over 80% agreement. There was no statistically significant difference in knowledge and application of gender-responsive pedagogy between teachers based on gender, school location, school type, and teaching experience.

Table 8.3

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 3 – The K-12 Curriculum

Table 12 shows the results gathered from the F-Test or Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 95% confidence level across all sessions (Session 1 to Session 9); the p-values are greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between the extent of implementation of IPBT per District in Schools Division of Marinduque. This means that the mode of completion (such as self-learning, peer coaching/mentoring, or Learning Action Cell) does not affect or influence the outcomes of these sessions within the educational program.

Further, the non-significant findings imply that regardless of how participants engage with these sessions, they achieve similar levels of understanding and proficiency in the covered topics. The mode of delivery may be a minor factor in determining the effectiveness of these sessions.

Accordingly, this is supported by the studies of Hammond (2006) and Fullan (2001), which emphasize the importance of effective program design, teacher training, and support mechanisms in ensuring the success of educational initiatives. These factors may contribute more significantly to program effectiveness than the mode of delivery itself.

Table 8.4

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 4 - Teaching Approaches

Table 13 shows the F-Test or Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) result at a 95% confidence level. Most sessions (Sessions 1 to 6) have p-values. The statistical analysis showed a value greater than **0.05**, indicating no significant difference in the degree of IPBT implementation across the districts in the Schools Division of Marinduque. This suggests that the mode of completion (such as self-learning, peer coaching/mentoring, or Learning Action Cell) does not significantly affect the result of these sessions within Module 4.

Session 7, about Classroom Management, is noteworthy as it has a p-value of 0.044. This indicates a **significant difference** at the 95% confidence level. This implies that the mode of completion significantly impacts the outcomes related to classroom management per District in Schools Division of Marinduque.

This contrasts with the study conducted by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), which examined the effectiveness of various teacher induction programs. The study revealed that while the specific components and structures of programs varied, there was generally no significant difference in teacher retention or student achievement outcomes based on the mode of delivery.

Table 8.5

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference of the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District of Module 5 – Learning Process and Module 6 - The School Community and Linkages

Table 14 shows the results generated from the F-test or Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at a 95% confidence level. It shows that all sessions in Modules 5 and 6 have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between the extent of implementation of IPBT in these modules per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque.

Which was employed in all sessions in module 5 and module 6, regardless of the mode of completion/implementation (self-learning, peer coaching/mentoring, and through Learning Action Cell (LAC)). As seen from the table, with all the p-values of more than **.05**, there is **no significant difference** in implementing the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque.

Further, the data implies that the mode of completion does not significantly impact the outcomes of the sessions within Modules 5 and 6. This means that regardless of how participants in each District engage with these sessions, they achieve similar levels of understanding and proficiency in the covered topics.

This is also parallel to the meta-analysis study conducted by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), which examined the effectiveness of various teacher induction programs. The study revealed that while the specific components and structures of programs varied, there was generally no significant difference in teacher retention or student achievement outcomes based on the mode of delivery.

Table 9

Statistical Data Showing the Significant Difference in the Extent of IPBT Implementation Per District Across Four (4) Areas

Table 13 shows the extent of implementation in the four areas (*Common and Specific Topic Discussed, Mentoring, Differentiated Instruction, and Formal Classroom Observation*) of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque as can be seen from the table, in the first area, *Common and Specific Topic Discussed*, District E has the most favorable response from the respondents, with a mean of 4.64 (Greatest Extent), in *Mentoring*, District F Ranked 1 had a general weighted mean of 4.76 (Greatest Extent), while District G has the highest

weighted mean of 4.70 (Greatest Extent) in Differentiated Instruction and formal classroom observation, with a weighted mean of 4.55. In General District F has the most favorable responses from the respondents in implementing IPBT, with a general weighted mean of 4.61 (Greatest Extent), followed by District E with a general weighted mean of 4.56 (Greatest Extent) and District G with a general weighted mean of 4.55 (Greatest Extent). Though District B had the lowest favorable responses from the respondents, its implementation is still to a Great Extent, with a general weighted mean of 4.16.

Regarding the significant difference in implementation per District across four areas of IPBT, using the chi-square test through SPSS software at a .05 significant level, the p-value is 1.00, the p-value is more significant than 0.05, which indicates that there is no significant difference between the extent of implementation of the Induction Program per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque. This is evident in the result of the recorded mean of each District, which is Great extent and Greatest Extent, which means that the teachers received appropriate technical assistance, guidance, and support from their schools and District in the entire Induction Program.

However, the findings in this study are in contrast to the findings of the study titled "Addressing Problems of Beginning Teachers: An Evaluation of Teacher Induction Programs." by Singleton (1999), which asserts that the implementation of Teacher's Induction Program in the State of Louisiana is not uniform or consistent in all schools. According to the result of this study, no uniform district-wide teacher induction program exists. The only policy with an equal footing that addresses the needs of new teachers is the annual orientation program about implementing the Teacher's Induction Program for beginning teachers; the rest is no longer uniform. Special services are provided to other schools that are not offered to the rest of the schools, which only receive little support or assistance.

Also, it revealed that the teacher participants know the local policies regarding implementing the Teacher Induction Program, specifically about the mentoring process. However, they did not have a clear vision of the expected output from the central office because there were no specific guidelines and requirements, and the central office did not monitor it.

The study further revealed that the state mandates on how the Teacher's Induction Program should be implemented are implemented differently than the lawmakers presented them. The original plan, as indicated, needed to be followed, and adjustments were made, which resulted in a different implementation scheme per school and District.

Part III and IV- Problems Encountered by the IPBT Participants and Their Suggested Solutions to Address the Problems During the Induction Program

Table 10

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Common and Specific Topics Discussed in IPBT

Table 14 shows the most prevalent problems encountered by some respondents and their suggested solutions under the common and specific topics discussed. The most commonly reported problem is "Too much workload/multiple tasks/conflict with other activities," accounting for 18.58% of responses and ranked first.

This finding parallels the result of the study of Hodges et al. (2020) and Means et al. (2013), which identified workload, technical issues, and time management as common challenges online learners face. These studies also emphasize the importance of clear communication, flexible scheduling, and adequate support services in addressing these challenges.

Regarding solutions to these problems, providing enough time to answer the modules is the most commonly suggested solution, with 34, or 30.09% of the respondents.

This is like the findings of the study of Smith and Jones (2018) titled "Time Management and Online Learning: Effects on Student Engagement and Achievement," which revealed the importance of providing students with adequate time to complete online modules and assignments. According to them, students reported feeling overwhelmed when faced with tight deadlines or unrealistic time constraints, negatively impacting their motivation and performance.

The table also reveals that only a few respondents encountered problems implementing IPBT in the first area. This is parallel to the results above, wherein all the discussions of the modules have a weighted mean of Greatest Extent, indicating that most of the respondents received appropriate guidance and assistance in understanding and completing the modules throughout the Induction Program.

Table 11

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Mentoring in IPBT

The table shows that the most prevalent problem encountered by some of the respondents in the mentoring area was schedule conflict between the mentors and the mentee, with 34 responses or 30.08% of the respondents. The least problem encountered was having mentors who needed better training, with two responses (1.77% of the respondents).

Such findings in this study are parallel to the result of the study (Ismail, 2019), which states that several challenges can hinder the effectiveness of mentoring: the need for more time and resources for mentoring activities, inadequate mentor training, unclear expectations, and mismatches between mentors and mentees can also impede the effectiveness of mentoring relationships. Additionally, the variability in the quality of mentoring experiences poses a significant challenge, as some mentees require more support or encounter conflicting advice from multiple mentors.

On the other hand, when it comes to the solutions suggested, creating a schedule for both the mentor and mentee ranked 1 with 37 or 32.74% of the respondents while providing a mentor with a designated time to assist the mentee ranked 2 with 8 or 7.08% of the respondents. Last in rank was assigning a specific peer/mentor per teacher, with 5 or 4.42% of the respondents.

This is similar to the study of (Ronfeldt et al., 2015), which asserts that to address the limited time and resources challenge, education policymakers and administrators must prioritize allocating dedicated time and funding for mentoring activities. This may involve scheduling regular mentor-mentee meetings during school hours, providing financial support for mentor training and resources, and ensuring mentors receive compensation or recognition for their efforts (Villani & Guarino, 2017).

In general, the suggested solutions entail that time/schedule is essential for a smooth mentoring flow among the mentors and mentees during the induction program, which indicates that a time schedule between the mentor and mentee is vital in a mentoring program.

Table 12

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Differentiated Supervision in IPBT

Table 16 shows the common problems encountered by some respondents in differentiated instruction and their suggested solutions. As can be seen from the table, the problem regarding confusion about the various techniques and strategies was addressed by 12 respondents (10.62% of the respondents). This is followed by challenging suggestions from different teachers, with five (5) responses or 4.42% of the respondents, while limited face-to-face classes to employ differentiated instruction practices and strategies was the last with 3 or 2.65% of the respondents because of the pandemic.

This is similar to the findings of the study of Smith et al. (2018), which explored teachers' challenges in implementing differentiated instruction strategies. They found that confusion about various techniques and strategies was a common barrier to effective implementation, leading to inconsistent practice and limited student engagement.

Similarly, Garcia et al. (2020) examined the collaborative processes among teachers in implementing differentiated instruction and identified conflicting suggestions

from different teachers as a challenge. They also recommended establishing consistent guidelines and collaboration frameworks to ensure alignment in instructional practices.

Meanwhile, regarding the suggested solutions to the problems encountered, providing technical support to the field ranked 1 with 5 or 4.42% of the respondents. Conducting regular training and upskilling for teachers ranked 2, with 4 or 3.54% of the respondents. Asking for assistance from colleagues regarding strategies/techniques they do not understand ranked last, with 3 or 2.65% of the respondents.

This is supported by the recommendations in the study (Smith & Davis, 2014), which states that a key solution to address challenges in differentiated supervision is to establish continuous improvement and feedback mechanisms. Schools can implement regular evaluation processes to assess the effectiveness of differentiated supervision practices and identify areas for refinement. This may involve collecting feedback from teachers, supervisors, and other stakeholders through surveys, focus groups, and observations, using data to inform decision-making and drive improvement efforts (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

The general results presented above indicate that teachers still need technical assistance, support, and training under the Induction program.

Table 13

Problems Encountered and Suggested Solutions in Implementing Formal Classroom Observation in IPBT

Table 17 shows that the common problems encountered by some respondents under the area of Formal Classroom Observation were less feedback and Technical Assistance, which should have been given to the teachers with 20 or 17.7% of the respondents. While not having the freedom to choose the class for the classroom observation and schedule of the Classroom Observation is not planned with the teacher both ranked 2 with 8 or 7.08% of the respondents. In comparison, lack of guidance in Daily Lesson Plan (DLP) Preparation ranked last with 8 or 7.08% of the respondents.

Such findings are parallel to Brown and Williams's (2018) study, which explored teachers' experiences with classroom observations and feedback processes. They identified restrictions on the freedom to choose classes for observation as a common concern among teachers. The study suggested establishing transparent protocols and fostering mutual trust between administrators and teachers to address this issue.

Similarly, in 2020, Smith found that unplanned or poorly scheduled observations negatively affected teacher confidence and performance. The study recommended involving teachers in scheduling and ensuring clear communication of observation expectations and objectives.

Among the solutions offered by the respondents, meeting the teacher first before sending out the class observation schedule ranked 1, with 8 or 7.08% of the respondents.

Providing technical assistance/guidance from the master teachers ranked 2 with 6 or 5.31%, while pre-observation in every classroom observation ranked last with 5 or 4.42% of the respondents.

This is supported by the findings of (Stronge, 2002). This revealed that utilizing a coaching method or feedback for observation can help create an environment of trust, teamwork, and ongoing development by promoting reflection, dialogue, and setting goals. In addition, by reframing observation practices as opportunities for growth and learning rather than evaluation, schools can instill a sense of optimism and hope for continuous improvement in the professional environment for new teachers (Hill & Grossman, 2013).

In general, the data above only indicates that the preparation and preparedness of the teachers to be observed are essential during formal classroom observations.

Part 5 - Proposed Enhancement Program as Suggested Intervention of the Researcher to Better Implement IPBT

The Enhancement Program of IPBT Implementation proposed by the researcher aims to improve the implementation of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers (IPBT) and address challenges newly hired teachers encounter. The program matrix outlines areas of concern, goals/objectives, projects/programs, implementing strategies, personnel involved, timeframes, required funding/resources, and evaluation/success indicators.

The crucial pre-implementation phase focuses on ensuring school preparedness, providing sufficient materials, scheduling task completion, and arranging mentoring. Key strategies include conducting comprehensive orientation sessions, preparing all necessary materials, scheduling tasks effectively, and arranging regular mentor-mentee meetings designed to provide the necessary support and guidance.

During the implementation phase, the program actively monitors mentee progress, demonstrates best teaching practices, facilitates engaging lesson planning workshops, plans formal classroom schedules, and conducts post-conferences. Strategies include effective tracking tools, structured observation, collaborative learning, and reflective frameworks, all of which aim to ensure a successful implementation.

In the post-implementation phase, the program conducts a comprehensive evaluation to assess the effectiveness of strategies, mentors, and mentees' performance. This includes data analysis, open forums, and reflection opportunities. The evaluation aims to clearly understand the IPBT implementation and mentor-mentee performance and address any concerns raised during open forums, ensuring the program's continuous improvement.

Overall, the program seeks to enhance the implementation of IPBT, support mentee development, and foster stakeholder collaboration. Evaluation tools, narrative reports, and progress records will measure program success and inform future improvements.

See Appendix A – Action Plan, for the complete and detailed information regarding the proposed enhancement program for the better implementation of IPBT.

Conclusions

Based on the preceding findings, overall, there is a Great Extent of implementation of the IPBT across the division. There is generally no significant difference in implementation across districts in four areas of IPBT implementation (common and specific topics, mentoring, differentiated instruction, and formal classroom observation). This indicates a **standardized approach to teacher induction within the division**.

However, significant differences in implementation were noted in specific sessions within Modules 2 and 4. Specifically, differences were observed in Module 2, Session 5 (Gender and Development) and Module 4, Session 7 (Classroom Management). **Therefore, the research hypothesis is accepted. There is a Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of IPBT Per District in the Schools Division of Marinduque.** These variations suggest areas where targeted interventions or adjustments may be needed to ensure consistency in program delivery.

Despite the overall Great Extent of IPBT implementation, several challenges persist. These include time constraints for completing modules, scheduling conflicts between mentors and mentees, and insufficient feedback and technical assistance for mentees. These challenges could undermine the program's effectiveness and impact teacher development and student learning outcomes.

The study identified suggested solutions to address these challenges, including providing more time to complete modules, establishing precise mentoring and classroom observation schedules, and enhancing feedback and technical support mechanisms. Implementing these solutions could mitigate the identified challenges and improve the overall effectiveness of the IPBT.

In conclusion, while implementing the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers in the Schools Division of Marinduque is in Great Extent, there is generally a **significant difference in IPBT implementation across districts**. There are still areas for improvement. Hence, the identified challenges and implementing suggested solutions shall be addressed to ensure that the program continues effectively supporting the professional growth and development of new teachers in the division.

Recommendations

Given the proceeding findings in this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Considering that some respondents cited "too much workload/multiple tasks/conflict with other activities" as a problem, it is recommended that teachers be given sufficient time to complete modules. This can be achieved by adjusting workload expectations or providing flexible deadlines. To address the challenge of limited time and resources,

education policymakers and administrators must prioritize allocating dedicated time and funding for mentoring activities (Ronfeldt et al., 2015).

2. Since the "Conflict availability schedule of mentor and mentee" was identified as an issue, it is crucial to establish precise schedules for mentoring sessions. Creating a structured mentor-mentee schedule ensures regular and practical support for new teachers. This may involve scheduling regular mentor-mentee meetings during school hours, providing financial support for mentor training and resources, and ensuring mentors receive compensation or recognition for their efforts (Villani & Guarino, 2017).
3. Given that "Confusion about the various techniques and strategies in differentiated instruction" was mentioned as a challenge, it is recommended that teachers receive technical support and guidance in implementing differentiated instruction strategies. This can include workshops, resources, and ongoing professional development opportunities focused on differentiated instruction. By investing in the professional growth of supervisors and mentors, schools can ensure that differentiated supervision practices are implemented with reliability and consistency (Smith & Davis, 2014).
4. To address the "Less Feedback and Technical Assistance given to the teachers," it is essential to enhance feedback mechanisms and provide technical assistance to support teachers during classroom observations. This can involve implementing structured feedback protocols, mentor training programs, and access to instructional support resources. Personalized support and mentorship help new teachers navigate the profession's challenges, developing a sense of efficacy and belonging (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).
5. Since "meet the teachers first before sending out the class observation schedule" was highlighted as a solution, it is advisable to prioritize communication and preparation for classroom observations. Establishing a pre-observation meeting between mentors and teachers can clarify observation objectives, expectations, and feedback processes—standardization of observation practices. Establishing clear, consistent observation protocols, such as a standardized checklist of teaching strategies, criteria, and rubrics, can enhance the reliability and validity of observation data (Hill & Grossman, 2013).
6. Regular monitoring and evaluation of IPBT implementation across districts should be conducted to identify any emerging challenges or areas for improvement. Additionally, ongoing support mechanisms, such as mentorship programs, professional development opportunities, and resource access, should be provided to sustain the program's effectiveness. Regular support, professional development opportunities, evaluation mechanisms, and assistance are necessary to recognize potential areas for enhancement and guarantee ongoing development (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

To the Division Office (Division IPBT Coordinator)

Aside from reports asked by the school heads to be submitted, they may conduct a surprise visit to see how each school implements and assists the newly hired/beginning

teachers relative to the programs of IPBT. In this case, they may see the actual scenario of each school in implementing the IPBT. Hence, a proper intervention will be provided.

They may also consider implementing the action plan crafted by the Researcher to improve the implementation of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers.

To the School Head and School IPBT Coordinator

They may conduct an open forum with the mentees or participants of the IPBT to have an open discussion about the problems that they met/encountered during the implementation of IPBT. That will provide an avenue for the mentors, mentees, and school heads to come up with an agreement and solutions to address the problems met/encountered.

To the Newly Hired Teachers/Mentees

They may have the courage to voice their concerns, problems, confusions, and difficulties encountered while completing the tasks and activities in the Induction program. That way, the right people in the program will adequately address their problems.

By implementing these recommendations, the Schools Division of Marinduque can enhance the effectiveness of the Induction Program for Beginning Teachers and better support new teachers' professional growth and development.

To Future Researchers

They may conduct further investigation or study to understand why there is a significant difference and how different modes of delivery may impact the effectiveness of gender-related professional development and classroom management practices of teachers in the school's division of Marinduque.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The Researcher hereby declared that permission was secured from the appropriate agency/institution regarding the participation of the respondents in this study. Further, the Researcher also acknowledged the anonymity of the respondents and their free will to participate in this study safeguarding their well-being, and that no conflict of interest existed within the conduct of the study. Moreover, this study strictly avoids plagiarism, there is no bias in the interpretation of findings, and results were used purely for the research intention.

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